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No. XXVII.

REPORTS MADE TO THE BOARD OF ADMIRALTY
AND THE BOARD OF TRADE, ON THE SUBJECT OF
PREPARING LEMON-JUICE TO RENDER IT AN
EFFICACIOUS ANTI-SCORBUTIC.

By SIR WILLIAM BURNETT, M.D., K.C.B.

Director-General of the Medical Department of the Navy.

As it appears likely that lemon-juice may be required to some considerable extent both for the navy and army, and as it is self-evident that this valuable article, without it be of genuine and first-rate quality, would be worse than useless in the treatment of Sea Scurvy, whether arising in the vessels at sea or among the troops on land, I have thought it an especial part of my duty to submit to their Lordships a copy of my correspondence, etc., with the Board of Admiralty and the Lords of the Privy Council in January, 1852, on the subject; and as the recommendations I then made have proved eminently successful, as fully evinced in the correspondence I then had the honour to have with the Privy Council, and having also on the arrival of Capt. McClure, of the Investigator, receiving the most truly gratifying account of its great success and beneficial influence in that ship, I consider it but right to make the same fully known to their Lordships, as a discovery or improvement in the preparation of lemon-juice, the value of which cannot be too highly estimated.

The following is an extract of a letter addressed to me on the 31st of October, 1854, by Dr. Armstrong, late Surgeon of the Investigator:—

“I have now the honour to inform you that I carefully tested the acids, viz., lemon-juice prepared as noticed in my letter of the 7th June, 1852, on leaving England, and at regular intervals subsequently throughout the entire period of the Commission up to the time of the abandonment of the ship, and accurately noted the results, that I might be enabled to arrive at a just estimate of their strength, and detect any deterioration which they might subsequently undergo.

“In the strength of acidity and power of neutralizing alkalies, I found both kinds far exceed in these properties the lemon-juice of commerce, or any that my professional experience had hitherto made me acquainted with. Although subjected to every possible vicissitude of temperature, from the highest Equatorial heat to the intensity of Arctic cold, I have been unable to detect the slightest change or deterioration in their strength and properties.

“To their great excellence as anti-scorbutic agents, I can with confidence bear the most ample testimony, for, unfortunately, I was afforded an opportunity of but too fully testing their efficacy when scurvy and scorbutic debility existed universally among us. To the great regularity which was observed in the daily issue of these acids, and the positive evidence which was afforded me that every officer and man drank their allowance, I attribute (as one of the principal causes) much of the comparative good health and freedom from scurvy which for a period of nearly the two first years we were engaged.

“When scurvy at length appeared so generally among us, I found the lemon-juice the most efficacious and speedy agent, not only in arresting its progress but in craduating the disease, until the influence of the causes which originally produce it (cold and insufficient food) again re-established it. I had recourse to it in all the scorbutic cases with the utmost confidence from the tried excellence of the acids. On it I placed the greatest reliance, it was my unfailing hope; and, as long as I could command a liberal supply, I was never disappointed in the anticipated results.

“I may also be permitted to remark, that it was not until some time after the supply of the acid for the use of the sick was much curtailed, in consequence of the diminished resources of the ship, as I was informed, that the number of our crew suffered any diminution by death after a period of more than three years had elapsed.

“I am also enabled to report favourably of it, as an external application to places or abrasions occurring in a scorbutic habit of body.

“I am, however, almost unable to say which kind of acid I could most strongly recommend as an anti-scorbutic,—the excellent acid properties of both I found equally unimpaired, and

in their relative efficacy I could detect no difference, but, as well as frequent observations enabled me to judge, the boiled acid deposited a larger amount of its mucilaginous constituents than the unboiled, or that which was prepared with spirit.”

The Enterprize, commanded by Captain Collinson, was also at the same time supplied with the lemon-juice, similarly prepared as that furnished to the Investigator, are the observations made by that officer on the subject:—In the course of the first winter symptoms of scurvy appeared in the warrant officers and the inmates, but yielded immediately to lime-juice; and remembering your recommendation of wine in lieu of spirits, I issued the former to them the ensuing winter, and they experienced no return of the disease.

“A few cases occurred the second winter, and upon our return from the travelling party in the spring of '53, two men as well as myself were slightly affected, which surprised me, as we were living upon pemmican and pork, the latter being well soaked during the whole period, and I can only account for it by the fact that we did not take lime-juice with us.”

And Mr. R. Anderson, late Surgeon of the Enterprize, in a letter dated Hong-Kong, in March, 1851, bears testimony to the high value of the lemon-juice in question in the following words:—

“The boiled lemon-juice is excellent; it has stood the trying changes of temperature, to which it has been subjected, without any deterioration whatever, and is superior to that prepared with the $\frac{1}{2}$ th of brandy, inasmuch as it contains a greater amount of acid in a given quantity of the liquid. I have tested both kinds from time to time, and always with the same results; half an ounce of the unboiled is neutralized by 23 grs. of the carbonate of potash; while the same quantity of the boiled requires no less than 28 grs.”

(Inclosure No. 1.)

Admiralty, January 7, 1852.

SIR,—I have received a letter of the 1st instant, written by order of the Lords of the Committee of Privy Council for Trade, on the subject of lemon-juice supplied, or to be supplied for use in merchant-vessels for the prevention or cure of sea scurvy; and I request you will inform their Lordships, that it is a subject to the elucidation of which my attention has been long and most anxiously directed. It is unnecessary to trouble their Lordships with the numerous experiments I have instituted with the view of arriving at a satisfactory result; but there are a few points which it is right should be stated, in order to the better understanding of the subject.

The ships of the fleet, during the many years I have had the Medical direction thereof, have seldom afforded anywhere an opportunity of trying the effects of remedial measures in the treatment of scurvy, and none whatever on the home station; I therefore, of necessity, was obliged to have recourse to convict-ships proceeding to some part of Australia, and in about 70 cases the Surgeons-Superintendent were directed to make trial of lemon-juice, citric acid, and nitrate of potash with vinegar. In several of these ships no opportunity presented itself. In a very large proportion (from various circumstances) no satisfactory conclusion could be arrived at; but in eight vessels in which the trial was fairly made, it appears by the reports of the Medical Officers, that the nitrate of potash has no remedial influence whatever,—it was, indeed, frequently injurious. The citric acid was, in many instances, useful as a remedy, but the lemon-juice was generally useful both as a remedy and a prophylactic.

It is notorious, however, that the lemon-juice supplied has for many years been very inferior in quality; and as this had proved the case in some late voyages, it was determined to try the effect of lemon-juice procured from the lemons squeezed in this country; and on the fitting out of the late Arctic Expedition, under Captain Austin, and that to Behring's Straits, under Captain Collinson, etc., this was carried into effect. Lemon-juice was formerly preserved by adding to it, in the shape of rum, 10 per cent. of alcohol. This lemon-juice never answered the end proposed, and it was, therefore, determined, after consultation with an able practical chemist, that one-half of the lemon-juice intended for the Northern Expeditions should be lightly boiled, then strained, and lastly, after being allowed completely to cool, bottled, bringing the juice in the bottle up to the neck; a small quantity of the best olive-oil was then poured over it, and the bottle corked, and the cork sealed over.

The second half was prepared by adding 10 per cent. of brandy, bottled, and oil poured over it in the same way. Both these experiments have proved eminently successful; and there never was lemon-juice so thoroughly preserved in all its qualities as

this has been; even after passing a winter in the Arctic Seas, it still retains its qualities as perfectly as when it was bottled; not one case of scurvy occurred in any of the ships-of-war during the whole time they were absent from England, viz., nineteen months.

In order to ascertain this to an undoubted certainty, two bottles of the lemon-juice, so prepared, were analysed in my presence by Dr. Bryson, my Professional Assistant, and Mr. Brown, Surgeon and Medical Storekeeper at Deptford Yard. The numbers in the following statement apply to the number of grains of carbonate of potash required to saturate half-ounce of the juice:—

	Grains.
1. Boiled lemon-juice, with oil on the surface required to saturate it	32
2. Not boiled, but 10 per cent. of brandy added, and covered with oil on the surface	29
3. Malta lemon-juice, obtained in Sicily, in the preparation of which great care was taken, and brandy or rum used	16

Then, it appears that the lemon-juice No. 1 is actually twice as strong as the lemon-juice No. 3, and will, in all probability, keep much better.

The price of lemon-juice is as follows:—

Last lemon-juice purchased in London.....	1s. 9d. per gallon.
Ditto Ditto Malta	1s. 10d. „

In addition to lemon-juice for the prevention and cure of scurvy, I beg to recommend the use of potatoes, and in default of the fresh root, the use of the preserved potato, which has cost the Victualling Department 43s. per cwt., and should be used at the rate of a quarter of a pound per man twice a-week as a prophylactic.

I regret troubling their Lordships with so lengthened a Report; but it did not seem to me that I could make them acquainted with the circumstances of this important case, without showing it in all its necessary bearings.

I am, Sir, your most humble Servant,
W. BURNETT, Director-General, &c.

The Secretary, Naval Department,
Board of Trade, Whitehall.

(No. 2.)

13, Salisbury Street, Strand, Oct. 22, 1854.

My dear Sir William,—Being perfectly aware of the interest that you took in the preparation of the lime-juice which was supplied to the Investigator upon her leaving England for her Polar voyage, in 1850, I think, now that we have returned in a state of health, which no other climate could have tested more severely, yet only sustaining a loss of four men and one officer over a period of nearly five years, an amount of mortality that few crews on any station do not exceed, and I wish to say a few words in favour of lime-juice.

You may remember, that the expedition which preceded the sailing of the Investigator, (Sir James Ross,) upon returning to England, were found to have suffered severely from scorbutic affection, and burying seven men in the short space of eighteen months. This state of things was attributed to the inferiority of the provisions supplied, and to the very bad quality of the lime-juice. This latter article was considered the prime cause, as, from its deteriorated condition, it possessed none, or very little anti-scorbutic properties; not so, however, with that prepared under your direction; for, from the first bottle that was opened in 1850, to the last in June, 1853, it retained both the aroma and the pungent taste of the lime, which made it the most welcome and grateful beverage to the crew; and, fortunately, having a large supply, I was enabled to put them on two ounces a-day for the first two years; this was, I am certain, one of our causes of good health; for, from its excellence, it became the favourite drink of the men, and, strange as it may appear, they preferred it to spirits even while travelling; frequently, when I have wished to encourage them, while toiling through heavy snow with a deeply-laden sledge, parched with thirst, and at each step sinking above the knee, have they redoubled their efforts while promising them an extra drink of lime-juice when we encamped. I do not think it is necessary to say much more in favour of giving men a good article, where health is concerned. I have always laid great weight upon that excellent anti-scorbutic when speaking of the health of my crew; may you hear the same from poor Collinson is the wish of

My dear Sir William, yours very truly,
(Signed) ROBERT McCLURE.

ABSTRACT OF
CASES OF ULCERATION OF THE STOMACH,
INSPECTED AT GUY'S DURING THE YEAR
COMMENCING OCTOBER, 1853.

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[Continued from page 612.]

THE three cases I have so briefly related have many points of similarity; and it would seem probable that each arose from irritation of the mucous membrane of the stomach, connected with disease of the liver, and great congestion of the portal system. In two the liver was cirrhotic; and in the third the patient was of very intemperate habits. These cases are sometimes found in connexion with great irritability of the stomach, and much relief is sometimes afforded by alkalies, associated with medicines which relieve portal congestion, and with the administration of the simplest forms of nourishing food.

The fourth case of simple ulceration of the stomach occurred in a young man, aged 22, a stone-mason, residing at Lambeth. He was admitted into Guy's, on March 20, and died the following day. As far as his history could be ascertained, it was found, that, during the previous winter, he had had pain at the stomach, and vomiting. He slightly improved; but, the day after Christmas day, he was confined to his bed from great pain at the stomach and vomiting. The vomited matters consisted of watery fluid. At that time he had *tie-douloureux*. On admission, the extremities were cold, and he almost powerless. His hands were blue. He had not had any diarrhoea, but had slight pain in the hypogastric region. He was sensible, and the pupils were much dilated. He rallied a little after admission, but vomiting of bilious matter came on, and he appeared to die from syncope. The inspection was made 17 hours after death. The body was tolerably nourished, but the skin was of a dingy hue. The brain and its membranes were normal, but there was slight sub-arachnoid effusion. In the chest, the trachea and bronchi were granular; and at the apices of the lungs were lobules of iron-grey consolidated lung, with some calcareous deposit. The right side of the heart was moderately distended; the left firmly contracted. On carefully examining the stomach, the cardiac extremity presented *post-mortem* solution; but towards the lesser curvature the mucous membrane was granular, and in several parts was destroyed by small patches of ulceration; these were quite superficial and irregular, and situated towards the lesser curvature. In other parts above the line of solution, there was arborescent injection. There was no thickening of the sub-mucous tissue; and the microscope only showed mucus and some granule cells. Brunner's glands in the duodenum, and the solitary glands and glands of Peyer, were very distinct in the ileum. The liver and spleen were healthy, the kidneys coarse, and the suprarenal capsules were small and atrophied. The pyrosis in this case appeared to be associated with an inflammatory condition of the mucous membrane; and this extended over a period of several months. The prostration was very remarkable. It is impossible to ascertain how far this condition arose from change in the large abdominal ganglia of the sympathetic nerve. These simple ulcers frequently cicatrize, and are afterwards scarcely perceptible. In a patient under Mr. Callaway's care, a short time ago, at Guy's, who died from epithelial cancer of the bladder, with calculus, he had hæmatemesis eighteen months before his death. On examining the stomach, a small cicatrix was observed; a slight puckering, and some fibrous tissue beneath the membrane were also observed.

CHRONIC ULCERATION.

Another form of ulceration is the chronic ulcer; and the three cases which have been inspected at Guy's during the present year, illustrate their form and position, and some of the modes in which a fatal termination takes place. A man, aged 37, had been subject to dyspepsia, constipation, general abdominal uneasiness, but no vomiting. Intense pain came on suddenly, and he died in a few hours. In the stomach was a circular ulcer, about the size of a 5s.-piece. The edges were rounded, and the mucous coat more extensively ulcerated than the muscular. The base of the ulcer was formed by the pancreas, covered by a dense layer of new tissue. The ulcer was situated close to the lesser curvature, and near the upper margin of the ulcer. Below the left lobe of the liver was a small perforation of the peritoneal coat—round, about a quarter of an inch in diameter. This had led to general peritonitis and speedy death. In this case the

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